

Bilkent University
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CS-439

Project Report

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24.05.2024

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1. Overview

Our project focuses on depicting performance and comparing KGenPRog and Nopol tools. We tested KGenProg and Nopol with their existing datasets and additionally tested the tools on other datasets such as Introclass. We wanted to determine which tool generates more plausible patches and is easier to install and use, as well as whether the performances reported in their original papers are replicable on datasets the tools were not tested on.

2. Tool Replication

KGenProg running on original dataset's Example01

```
C:\Users\Maryam Azimli\Downloads\kGenProg-1.8.2>cd kGenProg/example/CloseToZero01
The system cannot find the path specified.

C:\Users\Maryam Azimli\Downloads\kGenProg-1.8.2>cd kGenProg-1.8.2

C:\Users\Maryam Azimli\Downloads\kGenProg-1.8.2\kGenProg-1.8.2>cd /example
The system cannot find the path specified.

C:\Users\Maryam Azimli\Downloads\kGenProg-1.8.2\kGenProg-1.8.2>cd example

C:\Users\Maryam Azimli\Downloads\kGenProg-1.8.2\kGenProg-1.8.2\example>cd CloseToZero01

C:\Users\Maryam Azimli\Downloads\kGenProg-1.8.2\kGenProg-1.8.2\example\CloseToZero01>java -jar ../kGenProg-1.8.2.jar -r
./ -s src/example/CloseToZero.java -t src/example/CloseToZeroTest.java
Error: Unable to access jarfile ../kGenProg-1.8.2.jar

C:\Users\Maryam Azimli\Downloads\kGenProg-1.8.2\kGenProg-1.8.2\example\CloseToZero01>java -jar ../../kGenProg-1.8.2.jar
-r ./ -s src/example/CloseToZero.java -t src/example/CloseToZeroTest.java
2024-05-23 15:34:49 [main] [INFO] KGenProgMain -
===== kGenProg Configuration =====
configPath = kgenprog.toml
rootDir = . (set by command line)
productPaths = [src/example/CloseToZero.java] (set by command line)
testPaths = [src/example/CloseToZeroTest.java] (set by command line)
classPaths = []
executionTests = []
outDir = kgenprog-out
logLevel = INFO
mutationGeneratingCount = 10
crossoverGeneratingCount = 10
headcount = 10
maxGeneration = 10
timeLimit = PT1M
testTimeLimit = PT10S
requiredSolutionsCount = 1
randomSeed = 0
scope = PACKAGE
```

```
Command Prompt
scope = PACKAGE
faultLocalization = Ochiai
mutationType = Simple
crossoverType = Random
firstVariantSelectionStrategy = Random
secondVariantSelectionStrategy = Random
isPatchOutput = false
isHistoryRecord = false
currentDirectory = C:\Users\Maryam Azimli\Downloads\kGenProg-1.8.2\kGenProg-1.8.2\example\CloseToZero01
version = 1.8.2
=====
2024-05-23 15:34:50 [main] [INFO] KGenProgMain - initial failed tests (1/4)
example.CloseToZeroTest.test03: expected:<0> but was:<1>

2024-05-23 15:34:50 [main] [INFO] KGenProgMain - GA started
2024-05-23 15:34:50 [main] [INFO] KGenProgMain - entered the era of 1st generation.
2024-05-23 15:34:50 [main] [INFO] KGenProgMain -

-----
Elapsed time: 0 seconds
Variants: generated 7, build-succeeded 3, build-failed 1, syntax-invalid 0, redundant 3
Fitness: max 1(1), min 0.75(2), ave 0.833
Test execution time: sum 30 ms, max 12 ms, min 8 ms

-----
2024-05-23 15:34:50 [main] [INFO] KGenProgMain - GA stopped
2024-05-23 15:34:50 [main] [INFO] PatchLogExporter - patch (v7)
--- example.CloseToZero
+++ example.CloseToZero
@@ -16,7 +16,6 @@
 */
 public int close_to_zero(int n) {
   if (n == 0) {
-    n++; // bug here
   } else if (n > 0) {
     n--;
   } else {
2024-05-23 15:34:50 [main] [INFO] KGenProgMain - Summary
Reached generation = 1
Generated variants = 7
Syntax valid variants = 7
Build succeeded variants = 3
Time elapsed = 0 seconds
Exit status = SUCCESS
```



```
maryazim@Mary:/mnt/c/Use x + v
Parsing --sourceBinaries /mnt/c/Users/Maryam_Azimli/nopol/nopol/test-projects/./target/classes --testBinaries /mnt/c/Users/Maryam_Azimli/nopol/nopol/test-pr
jects/./target/test-classes --class symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExampleTest --tests symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExampleTest#tes
t4:symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExampleTest#test5:symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExampleTest#test2:symbolic_examples.symbolic_exampl
e_1.NopolExampleTest#test3:symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExampleTest#test1:symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExampleTest#test8:symbolic_
examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExampleTest#test9:symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExampleTest#test6:symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExa
mpleTest#test7 --coverage-detail DETAIL_COMPRESSED --nb-failing-load-class 0
Some test(s) failed during computation of coverage:
symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExampleTest#test5(symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExampleTest): String index out of range: -5
symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExampleTest#test6(symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExampleTest): String index out of range: -1
File saved to the following path: /mnt/c/Users/Maryam_Azimli/nopol/nopol/test-projects/target/CoveredTestResultPerTest.dat
[137768] INFO CoverageRunner - Tests found: 9
[137768] INFO CoverageRunner - Tests executed: 9
-126608641
-126608641
[149623] INFO SMTNopolSynthesizer - Not enough specifications: 0. A trivial patch is "true" or "false", please write new tests specifying SourceLocation sym
bolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExample:15.
-126608641
-126608641
-126608641
-126608641
-126608641
-126608641
[181745] INFO TestPatch - Applying patch: symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExample:12: CONDITIONAL index < 1
[188305] INFO TestPatch - Running test suite to check the patch "index < 1" is working
[188357] INFO NoPol - ----INFORMATION----
[188372] INFO NoPol - Nb classes : 97
[188372] INFO NoPol - Nb methods : 85
[188373] INFO NoPol - Nb Statements Analyzed : 2
[188373] INFO NoPol - Nb Statements with Angelic Value Found : 1
[188373] INFO NoPol - Nb inputs in SMT : 7
[188373] INFO NoPol - Nb SMT Level: 2
[188373] INFO NoPol - Nb SMT components: [4] [== of arity: 2, != of arity: 2, < of arity: 2, <= of arity: 2]
[188373] INFO NoPol - class java.lang.Boolean: 4
[188373] INFO NoPol - Nb variables in SMT : 16
[188373] INFO NoPol - NoPol Execution time : 188358ms
[188373] INFO NoPol -
[188373] INFO NoPol - ----PATCH FOUND----
[188373] INFO NoPol - index < 1
[188374] INFO NoPol - Nb test that executes the patch: 9
[188374] INFO NoPol - symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExample:12: CONDITIONAL
[188399] INFO NoPol - --- a/src/main/java/symbolic_examples/symbolic_example_1/NopolExample.java
+++ b/src/main/java/symbolic_examples/symbolic_example_1/NopolExample.java
@@ -11,4 +11,4 @@

boolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExample:15.
-126608641
-126608641
-126608641
-126608641
-126608641
-126608641
[181745] INFO TestPatch - Applying patch: symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExample:12: CONDITIONAL index < 1
[188305] INFO TestPatch - Running test suite to check the patch "index < 1" is working
[188357] INFO NoPol - ----INFORMATION----
[188372] INFO NoPol - Nb classes : 97
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[188373] INFO NoPol - Nb Statements Analyzed : 2
[188373] INFO NoPol - Nb Statements with Angelic Value Found : 1
[188373] INFO NoPol - Nb inputs in SMT : 7
[188373] INFO NoPol - Nb SMT Level: 2
[188373] INFO NoPol - Nb SMT components: [4] [== of arity: 2, != of arity: 2, < of arity: 2, <= of arity: 2]
[188373] INFO NoPol - class java.lang.Boolean: 4
[188373] INFO NoPol - Nb variables in SMT : 16
[188373] INFO NoPol - NoPol Execution time : 188358ms
[188373] INFO NoPol -
[188373] INFO NoPol - ----PATCH FOUND----
[188373] INFO NoPol - index < 1
[188374] INFO NoPol - Nb test that executes the patch: 9
[188374] INFO NoPol - symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExample:12: CONDITIONAL
[188399] INFO NoPol - --- a/src/main/java/symbolic_examples/symbolic_example_1/NopolExample.java
+++ b/src/main/java/symbolic_examples/symbolic_example_1/NopolExample.java
@@ -11,4 +11,4 @@

- if ( index == 0 ) // Fix index <= 0
-   return s.charAt(0);
+ if ( index < 1 ) // Fix index <= 0
+   return s.charAt(0);

PATCH
maryazim@Mary:/mnt/c/Users/Maryam_Azimli/nopol/nopol/test-projects$ |
```

3. New Benchmarks

Originally KGenProg used defects4j benchmark. As a new dataset, we chose Introclass' first half dataset and the nopol tool's dataset. Both defects4j and Introclass consist of reproducible Java bugs. They have 2 folders for each bug, main and test, which perfectly aligns with the usage tools require.

Originally Nopol used its own dataset:

4.2 Dataset of Real-World Bugs

NOPOL focuses on repairing conditional bugs, i.e., bugs in IF conditions and preconditions. Hence, we build a dataset of 22 real-world bugs of buggy IF conditions and missing preconditions. Since our prototype implementation of NOPOL repairs Java code, these 22 bugs are selected from two open-source Java projects, Apache Commons Math⁶ and Apache Commons Lang⁷ (*Math* and *Lang* for short, respectively).

As an addition, we tested the Nopol tool with the defects4j and Introclass dataset. Again, both of these datasets consist of reproducible Java bugs and have two files for each example: main and test. Introclasses tests were not enough to use for Nopol tool.

4. Results

“Presentation of figures and tables showing execution times, number of generated patches, plausible patch positions, etc.” stats

As we can see this table shows that KGenPRog requires more time to execute Nopol dataset.

As we can see this time Nopol tool takes much longer. No Execution time of Introclass is given as most of the patches were not plausible and each of them took over 30 minutes, resulting in an automatic stop.

Nopol tool with nopol dataset

KGenProg using Nopol's Dataset

■ Already Passes ■ Plausible patch ■ Fail

meta-chart.com

Introclass Dataset with Nopol Tool

■ Already Passed ■ Plausible patch ■ Fail

meta-chart.com

■ Already Passes ■ Plausible ■ Fail

meta-chart.com

Patch generation results for KgenProg on introclass benchmark

Patch generation results for KgenProg on the original Defects4j benchmark

■ Already Passes ■ Plausible ■ Fail

meta-chart.com

Nopol tool with Defects4j's dataset

■ Already Passes ■ Plausible patch ■ Fail

meta-chart.com

5. Discussion

What we speculated is that in general Nopol works much faster than defects4j. Nopol shares better results by producing more plausible patches when tested with its own dataset. However, KGenPRog shows much better results when it and Nopol are tested with defects4j examples within the KgenProg directory. Overall KGenProg Generated more plausible patches, but it also took much longer in terms of time.

Regarding Introclass benchmark, Nopol did not generate any plausible patches from 20 tests,

6. Replication Instructions

“Detailed instructions on replicating your project results. Detailed instructions on installing, building, and executing the tools and benchmarks”

To install KGenProg and make it work with its existing benchmark defects4j: follow this sites instructions:

<https://github.com/kusumotolab/kGenProg>

1. Download jar file, then clone the repo. Put jar file in the same folder as all the other directories inside KGenProg-1.8.2.
2. Go to the example file you want to test the tool with, for example:
`$ cd kGenProg-1.8.2/example/CloseToZero01`
3. To run the tool on an example:
`$ java -jar path/to/kGenProg-1.8.2.jar -r ./ -s src/example/CloseToZero.java -t src/example/CloseToZeroTest.java`
If the jar file is inside of KGenProg-1.8.2: then this is the way to run it:
`$ java -jar ../kGenProg-1.8.2.jar -r ./ -s src/example/CloseToZero.java -t src/example/CloseToZeroTest.java`
4. We have a script file that will run the all the examples of original dataset, to run it simply do: `python scriptName.py`
To test other examples manually change the directory.

To run KGenProg with introclass dataset:

* Make sure introclass dataset is in the shortest path possible as some directories names are too long for it. I kept it in “c:/Users/introclass” to make it as short as possible. We have a script to run introclass’s examples. It limits run time to 30 minutes as some of them might take much longer. Place the script file inside KGenProg-1.8.2 and run it this way:

```
$ cd KGenProg-1.8.2
```

```
$ python script.py
```

Adjust the path of introclass within the script to the appropriate one.

To run KGenProg with Nopol’s dataset:

Same as running introclass dataset. The script to run the dataset is called `run_kgenprog_with_nopol_dataset.py`. Place this script inside `kgenprog-1.8.2` and modify the path to suit the one you have and then run it
`$ cd KGenProg-1.8.2.`

```
$ python script.py
```

Install and run Nopol with its dataset:

1. Follow instructions given in here: <https://github.com/SpoonLabs/nopol>
2. **IMPORTANT:** Nopol runs on linux. So in case, you are using Windows like me, download ubuntu.
3. You will need to download several dependencies if any of this lines do not work for you, such as Java.
4. Clone repo:

```
$ git clone https://github.com/SpoonLabs/nopol.git
```
5.

```
$ cd nopol/nopol
```
6.

```
$ export JAVA_HOME=/usr/lib/jvm/java-8-openjdk-amd64
```
7.

```
# -DskipTests
```

 is required, to run the tests one needs to compile `../test-projects/` (see below)
8. Download maven if you already dont have it:

```
$ mvn package -DskipTests
```
9. To check if it was built correctly locate the jar file:

```
$ ls target/*jar
```

Output should be like this:

```
target/nopol-0.2-SNAPSHOT.jar  
target/nopol-0.2-SNAPSHOT-jar-with-dependencies.jar # we use this one
```

As mentioned in the repo readme, to run the examples we will use this jar “nopol-0.2-SNAPSHOT-jar-with-dependencies.jar”
10. To be able to run the tests we will need to first compile them so that respective classes are created. In case you want to test this tool with additional datasets you will need to adjust the test-projects folder severely, I will mention that below in more detail.

```
$ cd ../test-projects/  
# compiling app (in target/classes) and tests (in target/test-classes), but don't run  
the tests (they obviously fail, because the goal is to repair them)  
$ mvn test -DskipTests
```
11. ****THE MOST IMPORTANT PART****

```
$ cd ../test-projects/  
$ java -jar nopol.jar -s src/main/java/ -c target/classes:target/test-  
classes:/home/<user>/m2/repository/junit/junit/4.11/junit-  
4.11.jar:/home/<user>/m2/repository/org/hamcrest/hamcrest-core/1.3/hamcrest-  
core-1.3.jar -t symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExampleTest \  
-p ../nopol/lib/z3/z3_for_linux
```

Hamcrest is NOT provided in the repo, you will need to download that. After downloading it put it in the same folder as junit jar. Adjust the paths accordingly. <user> should be changed for the username inside home directory. All paths should be changed to according where exactly they are located. It took me so

much time to figure out the paths etc. To test this with other examples look at the test-projects/src/test/java folder there are several folders with different bug types and examples within them.

The way I ran it after changing some paths was:

```
maryazim@Mary:/mnt/c/Users/Maryam_Azimli/nopol/nopol/test-projects$ java -jar
"/mnt/c/Users/Maryam_Azimli/nopol/nopol/nopol/target/nopol-0.2-SNAPSHOT-jar-with-
dependencies.jar" -s "src/main/java/" -c "target/classes:target/test-
classes:/mnt/c/Users/Maryam_Azimli/nopol/nopol/nopol/lib/junit-
4.11.jar:/mnt/c/Users/Maryam_Azimli/nopol/nopol/nopol/lib/hamcrest-core-1.3.jar" -t
"symbolic_examples.symbolic_example_1.NopolExampleTest" -p
"/mnt/c/Users/Maryam_Azimli/nopol/nopol/nopol/lib/z3/z3_for_linux"
```

We have a script file to run all the examples of the original Nopol dataset under name: run_nopol_tests.sh. It runs the examples and produces the patches in the test-projects/patches directory. Before running make it executable:

```
$ chmod +x run_nopol_tests.sh
```

****IMPORTANT****

Previously the directory my code was in had a gap in the name, causing many issues, so if possible put the repo in a folder without any gaps within the path. If you are not able to, create a folder within c:/users, and adjust the properties of user to allow everything including, read-write, delete, and modify:

After this there shouldn't be any kind of issue.

Running Nopol with defects4j examples taken from KGenProg folder:

1. First, you will need to add the files to the Nopol/test-projects/src/main and test folders. Make sure the files main and test are on the same level as other already provided examples, for example: create a directory within test-projects/src/main/java name it defects4j_examples. Then add all the examples in there in these format /defects4j_examples/defects4j_example_1 and main file in there. Do the same thing for the test files. For example add Countdown.java to src/main/java/defects4j_examples/defects4j_example_1 and CountdownTest.java to src/test/java/defects4j_examples/defects4j_example_1.
2. After you are done adding all the examples into respective folders open Nopol/test-projects/target/maven-status/maven_compiler_plugin. There will be two folders compile and testCompile, these folders are for compiling and creating example.class and exampleTest.class. Open Folders and adjust this file : InputFiles.lst. As you see, it has all the paths for original dataset, follow the same format and structure and add the new dataset examples in there. Make sure to add main java files into "path\to\nopol\test-projects\target\maven-status\maven-compiler-plugin\compile\default-compile\inputFiles.lst" and tests to "path\to\nopol\test-projects\target\maven-status\maven-compiler-plugin\testCompile\default-testCompile\inputFiles.lst"
3. After doing this, save the files, open linux folder and remove previous builds with this line:

```
maryazim@Mary:/mnt/c/Users/Maryam_Azimli/nopol/nopol/test-projects$ rm -rf target/classes/*
```

```
maryazim@Mary:/mnt/c/Users/Maryam_Azimli/nopol/nopol/test-projects$ rm -rf target/test-classes/*
```

And Then build/compile again:

```
$ mvn test -DskipTests
```

If there are any error lines while compiling, carefully read them. Sometimes you need to adjust the class names etc within test files, also use only the libraries previously defined in original dataset.

The script to run defetc4j with nopol: run_defects4j_tests.sh. Before running make it executable:

```
$ chmod +x run_defects4j_tests.sh
```

The generated patches are sved into test-projects/defects4j_patches. Please adjust the script to match the directory paths of your repo.

Running Nopol with IntroClass:

Pretty much same as for defects4j. We used only blackbox tests.

1. Add main and tests to the respective folders
2. Adjust maven-status compile paths by adding each new example's path, save it
3. Delete previous compiles and builds with:

```
maryazim@Mary:/mnt/c/Users/Maryam_Azimli/nopol/nopol/test-projects$ rm -rf target/classes/*
```

```
maryazim@Mary:/mnt/c/Users/Maryam_Azimli/nopol/nopol/test-projects$ rm -rf target/test-classes/*
```

And Then build/compile again:

```
$ mvn test -DskipTests
```

4. Test one file to check the output patch.
5. We have a script to run all introclass examples(first half it):
run_introclass_tests.sh
6. Make the script executable: \$ chmod +x run_introclass_tests.sh
7. Patches are saved into test-projects/introclass.

7. Data Repository Link

“Link to a repository on [Figshare](#) or [Zenodo](#) containing the project code and all generated data (e.g., patches, execution logs). Please upload the artifacts only on Figshare or Zenodo.”